

Software innovation for inventors with TRIZ: an ToolKit assisted by integrated manufacturing systems and simulation

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Abstract

This research considers the approach and development made in a proposal of innovation software that integrates synergistically a virtual generator system. It is an instrument of design, analysis, simulation and interfaces of manufacture, relies on with the functions SIM and the TRIZ methodology tools. The function of the software uses libraries, an extensive base of knowledge, developed and verified previous cases. The reuse of existing design elements is a set of reusable knowledge that have proven their effectiveness if appropriate inventive principles are used. The TRIZ methodology is a very propitious tool to invent innovative and functional products, it has several tools to assist in the innovation process.

Key words: TRIZ, innovation, software, integrated manufacturing systems

Introduction

Innovation is an essential element in establishing competitive advantages and represents a component of economic development in companies. In Mexico, technological advancement and innovation is a continuous requirement of companies, facing the demands of global competition in international markets (CONACYT, 2014). Innovation implies a complex process that is promoted by economic, technical and social factors, it is also a process that requires creativity to begin and conceive a significant variety of contributions (López, R., Salas, A., Hernández, D., Cortes, R. & Alor, G., 2010). The TRIZ methodology is a very favorable tool for inventing innovative, functional and attractive products for potential customers; TRIZ has several tools to help users in the innovation process (Oropeza, R., 2011). Each of TRIZ tools serves as an innovation filter to find improvement resources or alternatives for innovative solutions for product design. That is why the TRIZ methodology is considered as a support instrument for innovators and an integrating element, that is, according to its creator, Genrich S. Altshuller, the TRIZ algorithm is a ladder for inventors, a method that takes a problem complex and what divides into several steps, through an organized creative process (Flores, G., Garnica, J. and Millán, E. A., 2014). TRIZ is a method that has been used for many years to develop new products and patents, it has proven to be very effective in the practical application of the fundamentals of Physics, Chemistry, mechanics and medicine, among other fields of knowledge. The fundamental principle is to find a particular solution of a general one, although it has been applied in a different field (Fernández, E. D., 2012). There are several documented success stories of companies, national and foreign universities that inform TRIZ as an amplifier of creative talent and researchers consider TRIZ as a platform that optimizes profits and production in a shorter time, compared to methods linear that were applied conventionally (Lemus, C., Domb, E., Hernández, J. C., Hernández, J. G., Mitre, H. A., García, A. y Manjárez, J. R., 2011). However, it is necessary to obtain accurate and reliable results in the product design, the solutions obtained, to be assisted by the use of software to assist in the design, manufacture and engineering of the product (Córdova, E., Flores, G., y Torres, S. J., 2006). It is of utmost importance the application of TRIZ together with CAD / CAM / CAE software and simulation, for the development of prototypes and the strengthening of innovative and inventive skills (Flores, G., Millán, E. A. y Flores, T., 2007).

TRIZ helps to systematically define current conflicts in the design of structured processes, through the use of inventive principles and their tools. TRIZ allows to meet the functionality requirements that are contradictory to the desirable characteristics of the product under development (Beltrán, E., Juárez, U. and Cortes, G., 2011). Cases

of studies have been reported in which through the use of TRIZ and specialized software, constructed objects can be used to obtain information on the early stages of the design process of said objects and thus accelerate product development, so There is an improvement in runtime, which has been shown to optimize the process. The use of this methodology achieves better results in terms of time(Cárdenas, C., Sosa, R. and Olvera, O., 2011). This research represents an approach to the integration of TRIZ algorithms together with the functions of software based on manufacturing systems integrated in the design and generation of new products. The goal is to maximize useful functions due to the challenges facing the industry. Many authors say that TRIZ can be used as an assistant, as well as its tools and technical elements that allow the systematization of the creative process (Fernández, E. D., 2012). With current technology, it is possible to identify the main companies that develop a certain line of research and reveal valuable information about the technological tren (Cantu, C. and Güemes, D., 2012). This research is an intangible technological development, an innovation software designed that is formed by a virtual generator system. The software is a solution to the high investment costs of the purchase, training and implementation of computer-aided design, manufacturing and engineering platforms to help the creative process in the design of new products. The software is an instrument of design, analysis, simulation and manufacturing interfaces, it has the functions of integrated manufacturing systems. It is through the application of the TRIZ methodology tools that it was possible to develop this proposal and achieve its implementation as part of its function. The software function uses libraries, a broad knowledge base, previous cases developed and verified.

Methodology

Description of the problem

The use of specialized computers and software (CAD / CAM / CAE) for the design of products, as instruments of support in different human activities has gained great importance, to the point that today it is almost inconceivable to live in a competitive world. Such tools, such as design software, have a high cost. The need to develop new products is a complicated activity that requires simple tools and at present this condition has not been verified compensated with the available software (Dadyko, O., Pérez, R. D., González, S. and Ramírez, H., 2012). It is considered that the personnel that work in the companies and the students dedicated to the development of the product, receive an incomplete instruction because they are taught the commands of the CAD software, but not the instruction of activities that allow the development of creativity and innovation. Creative designers have better salaries and are highly desired by companies. It is of the utmost importance for the implementation of TRIZ together with the software necessary for the development of models and the development of creative skills. (Martínez, L., Zapata, A., Castillo, B. E. and Hernández, V., 2011). Creativity is a central and necessary database for the stages of the process of developing new products, to propose inventive solutions that are likely to evolve. To achieve this objective, it is necessary to integrate innovation techniques and a new progressive algorithm.

Companies need new technologies and more adapted approaches to preserve or increase their capacity for innovation. The creation of new successful products is essentially a multidisciplinary process and the development of an innovative product should be guided by the concept of ideality, typical of the TRIZ methodology approach and backed by software that provides an economy of time and material resources. In a company, the objective is to avoid wasting resources and reworking so that the accuracy and creation of products close to the needs of customers in the first attempt is extremely desirable (Montiel, A. and Montalvo, N., 2012). It is undeniable that there is great competition from companies in the world whose competitive advantage in greater proportion develops in technologies to minimize production time and costs. Several companies and institutions need to buy specific software for fast and reliable results. While the possibility of having a computer-assisted tool is a competitive advantage for companies, the acquisition and implementation process is certainly complex. At the time of acquiring the software, 50% of the investment refers to the payment of the license and another 50% includes the training and adaptation of the technical requests of the software, which in most cases results in very high investments .

In this context, software users have had to search and master the diversity of options offered by commercial companies. For their part, TRIZ experts have applied the independent methodology to the use of specialized computer programs. Until now, there is insufficient creation of software alternatives that integrate TRIZ into product innovation processes (Guided Brainstorming LLC, 2015). It is worth mentioning that there is no 3D graphic interface that helps the creative process with TRIZ because so far only the contributions of the databases and the

relationship of variables have been covered to provide conceptual recommendations through some tools such as the matrix of contradictions, field diagrams, substance and technological monitoring of patents.

Innovation software development stages with TRIZ tools

The proposed design process for innovation software with TRIZ tools is described in three main stages:

1. First Stage: Product Design and Development
2. Second Stage: Methodological Measures
3. Third Stage: customer

Figure 1 describes in general the methodology used to design, develop and structure the proposed innovation software.

Figure 1. Innovation software development stages with TRIZ tools

The first stage corresponds to the design and development of products. The first stage fully shows the need to understand the operation of real conditions, their elements, relationships and objectives to create a system. This step helps us to have a very close idea of the components in which the simulation software will be carried out, thus determining the appropriate TRIZ tool to obtain results at a lower cost. For this stage the following aspects are considered objectives, results to be achieved, time required, resources required and scope of the function. The variables of interest, whether decisions and answers, are also considered. These variables are the elements that define the behavior and are relevant to its operation, which is represented in a generic way. The second stage establishes the phase of methodological measures. At this stage the design needs are identified where it is necessary to make a general plan that involves the specific tasks and selection of appropriate TRIZ tools. In the specific tasks the programs that will be used in the development of the innovation software simulation are considered. It is necessary to establish which functions of the program are adapted to the system to be simulated. The selection of the appropriate TRIZ tools establishes as factors to consider for their application the number of people involved in the innovation process, the cost of the process and the investment and establishes how long each of the simulation phases will take. It is possible at this stage to know the expected results at the end

of each stage, that is, with the time already established for each stage, the result must be established in each of them, which can help monitor the progress of the entire process of simulation. The sources of information are also defined in this step, so that data collection is closely linked to the duration of the application of the model, since the time required to obtain the information depends on it. At this stage, the data collected regarding the previously defined variables are studied in order to establish their behavior and that they will be introduced into the simulation software so that it can be ensured that the simulation parameters work correctly according to the behavior system original. In the third stage concerning the client, the business and market aspects for decision-making are considered. Once the relevant analyzes and the presentation of the corresponding report have been carried out, it is necessary that the people involved, make decisions based on the costs involved in the labor involved, possible delays of the operation due to the changes and the time that it will take to make the proposed changes. Finally make conclusions and recommendations of the process. Figure 2 shows the structure of the analysis of each stage contained in the methodology for the development of innovation software with TRIZ tools.

Figure 2. Structure of the analysis of each stage contained in the methodology for the development of innovation software with TRIZ tools.

Based on the above, the proposed innovation software that integrates a virtual generator system is developed. It is an alternative for companies, organizations and institutions that do not have high economic resources and require software support for the development of innovation and engineering projects. It is an instrument of design, analysis, simulation and manufacturing interfaces, it offers the advantage of having computer-assisted engineering programs for SIM (Integrated Manufacturing Systems) functions, guided by TRIZ tools.

Results and Discussion

The function of the software uses libraries, an extensive base of knowledge; previous cases developed and verified under the license GNU. When recycling existing design elements, there is a set of reusable knowledge that has verified its effectiveness if the appropriate inventive principle is used (Beltrán, E., Juárez, U. and Cortés, G., 2012). It is based on a collaborative structure that allows the application of basic knowledge and facilitates the transfer of knowledge; It also describes and creates the conditions to allow open innovation, collaboration and software

architecture services. The collaborative environment helps guide creativity and unite the requirements of problems with models tested in engineering and with specific experiences derived from their application (López, R., et al., 2010). In Figure 3, the follow-up of the process of compiling libraries available in C of the Open Cascade Technology Public License is proposed, to make a proposal on the Windows platform and, on the other hand, to migrate the C code to Java, to have a multiplatform option, through the architecture in Linux.

Figure 3. Summary of compilation of available libraries and modular structure of the OPEN CASCADE

OPEN Cascade is a powerful platform to develop 3D design programs that model applications. It consists of C reusable object libraries and a development hardware system that are available in open source. It includes components for 3D surface and solid modeling, visualization, data exchange and rapid function development. It can be applied in the development of numerical software, including CAD / CAM / CAE and simulation. It was decided to use OPEN CASCADE because by having access to the source code of the existing applications that have been tested, it provides additional stability and resistance to the solutions and uses. This code can be freely adapted, modified and enriched by the necessary functionality according to the particular needs of the programmer. The open cascade is open source and there are no license fees, as long as the company's terms are met, which prohibits the benefit of programs generated without prior authorization. This structure is mainly divided into: Class base, data modeling, modeling algorithms, coupling, visualization, data exchange (standardized), application of work forms (OCAF), GUI work forms and development tools. The use of object-oriented programming allowed linking other concurrent engineering integration functions as a current technological trend. The innovation program is in the process of creating modules to create an interface that can be used by people who are familiar with some computer-aided design concepts or any user who has basic computer skills. Figure 4 shows the main display window with the shortcuts of the functions of the technology support libraries to generate routines oriented to the specific use of the software.

Figure 4. Main display window Innovation software with TRIZ tools

This development is considered a competitive advantage in the product innovation process, due to the reduction of costs, time and effort. Some applications of the 3D graphic environment for software use are illustrated in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Applications of the 3D graphic environment for software

Future work

It is necessary to keep the research in constant feedback to update the trends of application of the TRIZ methodology, which have demonstrated its growth and expansion from various fields of knowledge. It is recommended to apply the model and make necessary adjustments for design functions, whose activity involves intangible resources. It is recommended to maintain technology surveillance and monitoring to update the versions of the virtual platform alternatives and library updates. It is important to mention that the functions of the program were considered for future use and to allow continuous improvement, the programming algorithm requires time and constant investigation of cases for its evolution, since it consists of the interrelation of modules that are integrated into the functions of TRIZ tools and design, analysis and simulation instruments. It is recommended to perform programming algorithms to automate the functions of the model from the different stages involved in its application. It is advisable to carry out studies regarding the application of TRIZ for the generation of software to assist in ergonomic design, simulation and integrated manufacturing systems. These technological tools require constant feedback that allows development that is accessible to Mexican companies that compete with the cutting-edge technologies of first world countries.

Conclusions

Program code handles object-oriented programming, remains open for constant feedback and progress of modules, functions and applications. Open Cascade Technology Public License Libraries provide flexibility for future input because it builds on an international collaborative community that performs continual updates and improvements to the code base. It is recommended to carry out the development and technological projects of computation in operating system and Linux platforms, since it provides the compatible elements, necessary and economically appropriate to expedite the processes of investigation and development, even It is possible to perform optimally the transfer of code of an exclusive language of an environment, to move them to a multiplatform application.

The proposed innovation software, offers a great diversity of advantages over the engineering software that are commercial, emphasizes the integration of the tools of TRIZ that assists and facilitates the fast learning, the manipulation of applications and orients to the creative process of product development. Another exclusive advantage is that it allows the import and export of projects, which provides compatibility and ease of use in combination of applications with other software. It is recommended to conduct studies in co-authorship and multidisciplinary collaboration to stimulate the scientific production and creation of new technologies,

with the participation of people from all sectors, whether academic, governmental, business and further promote the participation of the social sector. To boost the culture of innovation in Mexico.

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